

NORMAL AND POLYMOLYBDATES OF SOME COMPLEX CATIONS AND THE COMPOSITION AND CONSTITUTION OF METAMOLYBDATES

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Normal and polymolybdates of some complex metal cations have been prepared and their properties studied, specially the dehydration of metamolybdates. The results have been found to support Rosenheim's scheme of formulation for the metamolybdates in preference to those advocated by Jander, Brintzinger, Keggin and others.

In a previous paper (Rây and Siddhanta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **18**, 397) the composition and constitution of paramolybdates were studied by preparing paramolybdates of a number of complex biguanide metal cations of high equivalent weight and examining their properties, specially that of dehydration. A similar study has been extended in the present paper to the metamolybdates. Incidentally some new normal and paramolybdates have also been described.

As in the case of paramolybdates different views are held regarding the composition of metamolybdates.

Rosenheim (Rosenheim and Felix, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1913, **79**, 292) on the basis of Werner's co-ordination theory represented metamolybdates as $R_n H_n [H_2 (Mo_2O_7)_6] aq.$ where R is a univalent positive radical.

Travers and Malaparade (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1926, **39**, 1406) from potentiometric titrations formulated metamolybdates as $R_2 Mo_6 O_{18}, aq.$

Jander and his co-workers (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, **180**, 129 ; 1930, **187**, 60 ; 1933, **211**, 49 ; **212**, 1 ; 1934, **217**, 65) from the results of ionic diffusion experiments, which were supported by those of conductometric and thermometric titrations, as well as from a study of absorption spectra, concluded that the metamolybdates should be represented by the formula, $R_3 [H_3 Mo_6 O_{21}] aq.$ which is closely related to that of Rosenheim, as the latter is obtained by doubling the former.

Britton and German (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **128**, 2154) from potentiometric titration and Bye (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1939, **6**, 174) from conductometric titration confirmed the formation of metamolybdates of the composition, $Na_2O, 4MoO_3.$

Brintzinger and Ratanarat (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1935, **224**, 97) from the measurement of the rate of electro dialysis of polymolybdate ions obtained values for the ionic weight of metamolybdates in good agreement with those of Jander.

From a consideration of co-ordination number in ionic crystals Pauling (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 1010, 2868) suggested that the metamolybdates should be represented by the formula, $H_6 [H_2O_4. Mo_{12}O_{18} (OH)_{36}]$.

Keggin (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1934, **144A**, 75) formulates the metamolybdates as $R_6 [H_2 Mo_{12} O_{40}] aq.$ from a consideration of crystal structure and the dehydration of twelve heteropolyacids.

In the present paper the dehydration of cobaltic trisbiguanide metamolybdate and triethylenediamine cobaltic metamolybdate was studied as they could be obtained in a pure state by precipitation from solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Chloromolybdate (Normal).—When a strong solution of sodium normal molybdate was added, drop by drop with stirring, to a large excess of that of cobaltic trisbiguanidinium hydrochloride (Rây and Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 621), a beautiful orange coloured crystalline product readily separated out. The crystals were washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol, and finally dried in air.

The product is soluble in hot water, but on recrystallisation from the latter it was found to undergo partial hydrolysis giving a mixture of chloro- and hydroxo-molybdates in the form of beautiful silky scales. Found : {N, 38'57; Cl, 6'51; Mo, 16'95; Co, 10'69.

$\left[\text{Co (BigH}^+)_3 \right] \begin{matrix} \text{Cl} \\ \text{MoO}_4 \end{matrix}$ requires N, 37'67; Cl, 6'37; Mo, 17'21; Co, 10'58 per cent; where BigH = one molecule of biguanide, $\text{C}_2\text{N}_3\text{H}_7$.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Normal Molybdate.—Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium hydrate (Rây and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) (2g.), dissolved in the least quantity of water, was mixed with a solution of sodium normal molybdate (1'8g.). The mixture was filtered and to the filtrate a solution of ammonium acetate (2g.) was added, drop by drop, with vigorous stirring. Reddish brown needle-shaped crystals appeared readily. These were washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The crystals were dried in air. The product is soluble in hot water. Found : {N, 31'82; Co, 8'90, 8'92; Mo, 22'04, 21'90; H_2O (by loss at 92°), 8'86.

$[\text{Co (BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{MoO}_4)_3, 6'5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 31'79; Co, 8'90; Mo, 21'80; H_2O , 8'85 per cent}.

On recrystallisation from hot water it gave a different hydrate in the form of beautiful deep red silky crystals. Found : {N, 33'28; Co, 9'34; Mo, 23'01. $[\text{Co (BigH}^+)_3]_2 (\text{MoO}_4)_3, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 33'38; Co, 9'38; Mo, 22'89 per cent}.

Nickel Biguanidinium Normal Molybdate.—A solution of nickel biguanidinium chloride (Rây and Purakayastha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **18**, 217) was added with stirring to that of sodium molybdate. Beautiful yellowish brown crystals of the product separated from the solution. These were washed and dried as usual. Found : {N, 29'53; Ni, 12'39; Mo, 20'37. $[\text{Ni (BigH}^+)_2] \text{MoO}_4, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 29'49; Ni, 12'37; Mo, 20'22 per cent}.

Copper Biguanidinium Normal Molybdate.—The substance was obtained as a beautiful violet crystalline precipitate by mixing a solution of copper biguanide chloride (Rây and Bagchi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 617) with that of sodium normal molybdate. The crystals were washed and dried as before. Found : {N, 29'66; Cu, 13'49; Mo, 21'01. $[\text{Cu (BigH}^+)_2] \text{MoO}_4, 2'5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires N, 29'75; Cu, 13'42; Mo, 20'40 per cent}.

Preparation of the complex metamolybdates presented some difficulties. Interaction of sodium metamolybdate with cobaltic trisbiguanidinium chloride in aqueous solution led to products of indefinite composition with a ratio of Co : Mo approximately equal to 1 : 2, in place of 1:6 as required for the metamolybdate. This seems to suggest that sodium metamolybdate in aqueous solution suffers partial hydrolysis with formation of lower molybdates. Digestion of the solid cobaltic trisbiguanidinium normal molybdate in a buffer solution of pH 2 also did

not give the desired product, though the range of stability of metamolybdates in aqueous solution lies between p_H 1.5 and 2.9. Even when a solution of the cobaltic trisbiguanidinium normal molybdate was substituted for the solid, no better results were obtained. The pure complex paramolybdate could, however, be obtained in this way by using a buffer solution of p_H 4 (approximately). The range of stability of the paramolybdates in solution lies between p_H 3 and 4.5.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Paramolybdate.—Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium normal molybdate (2g.) was dissolved in 50 c.c. of water on the water-bath. The solution was filtered and added, drop by drop with stirring, to that of a buffer solution of p_H 4, made by mixing 200 c.c. acetic acid (0.2*N*) and 50 c.c. of sodium acetate solution (0.2*N*). The mixture was then heated on the water-bath for 10-15 minutes. The dull red crystalline precipitate was washed and dried as usual. Found: {N, 21.56; Co, 6.21, 6.10; Mo, 34.50, 34.53.

[Co (BigH⁺)₃]₂ (Mo₇O₂₄), 9H₂O requires N, 21.64; Co, 6.07; Mo, 34.61 per cent}.

Prepared in a different way this compound has already been described by Rây and Siddhanta (*loc. cit.*).

Pure complex metamolybdate was finally obtained from a nitric acid solution of p_H 2.5 (approximately) in which cobaltic trisbiguanidinium nitrate and sodium metamolybdate were made to react.

Cobaltic trisBiguanidinium Metamolybdate.—Light yellow crystals of sodium metamolybdate were obtained by allowing an acid solution of sodium normal molybdate (1g. Na₂MoO₄, 2H₂O dissolved in 6.2 c.c. of *N*-HCl) to evaporate in air at the room temperature for about 10-15 days. The crystals were washed first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. They were dried in air. Found: {Na, 6.31; Mo, 52.26, 52.12. Na₂O.4MoO₃, 5H₂O requires Na, 6.32; Mo, 52.74 per cent}.

Cobaltic trisbiguanidinium nitrate (1g.), (Rây and Dutt, *loc. cit.*) was dissolved in the least quantity of nitric acid of p_H 2.5 (approx.) in the cold. This was then added, drop by drop with stirring, to a solution of sodium metamolybdate (2g.) in the same solvent. A beautiful pale violet precipitate appeared. The mixture was set aside to settle. The precipitate was filtered, washed free of nitric acid first with ice-cold water and then with alcohol. The product was dried in air. The substance is insoluble in water and dilute acids. Found: {N, 15.07; Co, 4.24, 4.26; Mo, 40.96, 41.48; H₂O (by loss at 100°), 7.98.

[Co(BigH⁺)₃]₂(H₆Mo₁₂O₄₂), 12.5H₂O requires N, 15.11; Co, 4.25; Mo, 41.45; H₂O, 8.06 per cent}.

Dehydration

Substance taken = 0.8804g.

Temp.	60°	70°	80°	90°	100°	110°
Loss of water in g.	0.0510	0.0608	0.0628	0.0654	0.0699	0.0698
„ in %	5.79	6.91	7.13	7.42	7.98	7.98
„ in moles	8.94	10.60	11.0	11.44	12.32	12.32

The product dehydrated at 100° gave on analysis: Co, 4.64; Mo, 45.28. [Co(BigH⁺)₃]₂ [H₆Mo₁₂O₄₂] requires Co, 4.61; Mo, 45.0 per cent. The dehydrated substance regained its original weight after a few days, on exposure to atmospheric air at the room temperature.

TrisEthylenediamine Cobaltic Metamolybdate.—A solution of sodium metamolybdate (1 g.) in dilute nitric acid ($p_n = 2.5$ approx.) was added drop by drop to that of *trisethylenediamine cobaltic chloride trihydrate* (1 g.) in the same solvent. A pale yellow flocculent precipitate separated from the solution. The product was allowed to settle, washed free of hydrochloric acid with ice-cold water and alcohol. It was then dried in air. {Found: N, 6.58; Co, 4.72, 4.64; Mo, 45.0, 45.28; H₂O (by loss at 100°), 9.59. [Co En₃]₂[H₆Mo₁₂O₄₂], 13.5H₂O requires, N, 6.59; Co, 4.63; Mo, 45.16; H₂O, 9.52 per cent}, where En=one molecule of ethylenediamine, C₂N₂H₈.

Dehydration.

Substance taken = 0.5632 g.

Temp.	60°	70°	80°	90°	100°	110°
Loss of water in g.	0.0369	0.0455	0.0496	0.0520	0.0540	0.0540
„ %	6.550	8.078	8.806	9.237	9.590	9.590
„ moles	9.30	11.50	12.56	13.06	13.56	13.56

The product dried at 100° gave on analysis: Co, 5.15; Mo, 49.79. [Co. En₃]₂[H₆Mo₁₂O₄₂] requires Co, 5.11; Mo, 49.90 per cent.

The dried substance regained its original weight on exposure to air for several days at the room temperature.

Another product on analysis gave: N, 6.71; Co, 4.66, 4.75; Mo, 45.45, 45.36; H₂O (by loss at 100°) 8.26. [Co.En₃]₂[H₆Mo₁₂O₄₂], 11.5H₂O requires N, 6.68; Co, 4.69; Mo, 45.81; H₂O, 8.19 per cent}.

Dehydration.

Substance = 0.8035 g.

Temp.	60°	70°	80°	90°	100°	110°
Loss of water in g.	0.0483	0.0569	0.0589	0.0622	0.0652	0.0664
%	6.01	7.08	7.33	7.74	8.12	8.26
moles	8.44	9.95	10.30	10.89	11.40	11.62

The product thus dehydrated gave on analysis: Co, 5.15; Mo, 49.79. [Co.En₃]₂[H₆Mo₁₂O₄₂] requires Co, 5.11; Mo, 49.90 per cent.

DISCUSSION

The results of dehydration experiments on the complex metamolybdates, summarised in Table I, show that the metamolybdates contain three molecules of bound or constitutional water.

TABLE I

Substance.	Loss of water in moles at						Gain of water in moles when exposed to air.
	60°	70°	80°	90°	100°	110°	
Cobaltic <i>trisbiguanidinium</i> metamolybdate [Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₃₆ , 15.5H ₂ O	8.94	10.60	11.0	11.44	12.32	12.32	12.30
Cobaltic <i>trisethylenediamine</i> metamolybdate [Co.En ₃] ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₃₆ , 16.5H ₂ O	9.30	11.50	12.56	13.66	13.56	13.56	13.50
„ „ 14.5H ₂ O	8.44	9.95	10.30	10.89	11.40	11.62	11.50

In Table II the composition of these metamolybdates are represented by formulae based on different views and their crystal water content compared with the experimentally determined values.

TABLE II

Substance.	Formula.	Crystal water calc.	Crystal water found
1. Cobaltic <i>tris</i> -biguanidinium metamolybdate	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₃₉ , 15.5H ₂ O (older formula)	10.04%	7.95%
	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ H ₄ [H ₂ (Mo ₂ O ₇) ₆], 12.5H ₂ O (Rosenheim)	8.06	
	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ [H ₃ Mo ₆ O ₂₁], 6.25H ₂ O (Jander)	8.06	
	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ [H ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₄₀], 14.5H ₂ O (Keggin)	9.39	
2. Cobaltic <i>tris</i> -ethylenediamine metamolybdate	[Co.En ₃] ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₃₉ , 16.5(14.5)H ₂ O (older formula)	11.64 (10.38)	9.59% (8.26)%
	[Co.En ₃] ₂ H ₄ [H ₂ (Mo ₂ O ₇) ₆], 13.5(11.5)H ₂ O (Rosenheim)	9.52 (8.23)	
	[Co.En ₃] ₂ [H ₃ Mo ₆ O ₂₁], 6.75(5.75)H ₂ O (Jander)	9.52 (8.23)	
	[Co.En ₃] ₂ [H ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₄₀], 15.5(13.5)H ₂ O (Keggin)	10.93 (9.66)	

In Table III the results of analysis of the dehydrated products are summarised for comparison with those required for the different formulae.

TABLE III

Substance.	Formula.	Found		Calc.	
		Co.	Mo.	Co.	Mo.
1. Cobaltic <i>tris</i> biguanidinium metamolybdate	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₃₉ (older formula)	4.72%	46.08%	4.64%	45.28%
	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ [H ₆ Mo ₁₂ O ₄₂] (Rosenheim)	4.62	45.11		
	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ [H ₃ Mo ₆ O ₂₁] (Jander)	4.62	45.11		
	[Co(BigH ⁺) ₃] ₂ [H ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₄₀] (Keggin)	4.69	45.75		
2. Cobaltic <i>tris</i> ethylene-diamine metamolybdate	[Co.En ₃] ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₃₉ (older formula)	5.24	51.11	5.15	49.79
	[Co.En ₃] ₂ [H ₆ Mo ₁₂ O ₄₂] (Rosenheim)	5.11	49.91		
	[Co.En ₃] ₂ [H ₃ Mo ₆ O ₂₁] (Jander)	5.11	49.91		
	[Co.En ₃] ₂ [H ₂ Mo ₁₂ O ₄₀] (Keggin)	5.19	50.70		

From an examination of these tables it will be clear that the experimental results support the scheme of formulation advocated by Rosenheim or Jander. But as it has been found by X-ray study that a six-fold aggregation cannot represent the metamolybdate, preference should be given to Rosenheim's formula. At the same time it must, however, be pointed out that this cannot altogether exclude Keggin's formulation as it is sometimes found that last one or two molecules of water of hydration in the case of some salts cannot be removed even when dried at or about 110° .

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